

Research Article

A new combination in *Caulokaempferia* (Zingiberaceae)

Rajeev Kumar Singh

Botanical Survey of India, Arid Zone Regional Centre, AIIMS Road, Jodhpur - 342014, Rajasthan, India

E-mail: rksbsiadsingh@gmail.com; ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-0136-9243>

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Abstract: A new combination is made for *Monolophus odontochilus* Y. H. Tan & H. B. Ding under the genus *Caulokaempferia* K. Larsen as *Caulokaempferia odontochila* (Y. H. Tan & H. B. Ding) R. Kr. Singh.

Keywords: Endemic, *Monolophus odontochilus*, Myanmar

Introduction

Caulokaempferia K. Larsen is represented by 35 species, distributed in East Himalaya, Indo-China to Southeast China (POWO, 2024). In Myanmar, the genus is represented by four species, namely *C. kayinensis* Picheans. & Sangnark, *C. monensis* Picheans. & Sangnark, *C. odontochila* (Y.H.Tan & H.B.Ding) R.Kr.Singh and *C. secunda* (Wall.) K.Larsen, of which *C. kayinensis*, *C. monensis* and *C. odontochila* are endemic (POWO, 2024). However, *Monolophus odontochilus* Y.H.Tan & H.B.Ding needs to be transferred to the genus *Caulokaempferia* (published by Larsen, 1964). Therefore, following recent circumscription of *Caulokaempferia*, a new combination is proposed here for *Monolophus odontochilus* under the genus *Caulokaempferia* as *C. odontochila* (Y.H.Tan & H.B.Ding) R.Kr.Singh.

The genus name *Monolophus* published by Wallich (1830) is invalid because it is a provisional name according to Article 36.1 in Turland *et al.* (2018). Later, *Monolophus* Wall. was validated by Endlicher (1837) and cited type species as *Kaempferia elegans* Wall. However, according to Article 38.1 in Turland *et al.* (2018), Delafosse *et al.* [Bull. Sci. Nat. Geol. 23(Table Gen.): 31. 1830] validly published *Monolophus* through direct reference to their previously published diagnoses for the genus and the species *Kaempferia elegans* Wall. (Bull. Sci. Nat. Geol. 23: 69. 1830). Therefore, it is clear that the genus name *Monolophus* (type: *Kaempferia elegans* Wall.) is synonymous to *Kaempferia* L. (type: *Kaempferia galanga* L.). Mood *et al.* (2014) treated *Caulokaempferia* K.Larsen as a superfluous name

for *Monolophus* Wall. ex Endl., which is not correct as per ICN (Turland *et al.*, 2018).

Nomenclature

Caulokaempferia K. Larsen, Bot. Tidsskr. 60: 166. 1964.

Type: *Kaempferia linearis* Wall. [≡ *Caulokaempferia linearis* (Wall.) K.Larsen].

Caulokaempferia odontochila (Y.H.Tan & H.B.Ding) R.Kr.Singh, *comb. nov.*

≡ *Monolophus odontochilus* Y.H.Tan & H.B.Ding, PhytoKeys 138: 156. 2020.

Holotype: Myanmar, Kachin State, Putao District, Gathu Village, 27°29'07.23"N 97°58'19.49"E, 643 m, 1 June 2018, Y.H. Tan, B. Yang, H.B. Ding, X.D. Zeng, M.B. Maw and H.L. Neing M3886 (HIBTC): isotypes RAF.

Distribution: Endemic to Kachin State, Myanmar.

Kaempferia L., Sp. Pl. [Linnaeus] 1: 2. 1753.

Type: *Kaempferia galanga* L.

= *Monolophus* Wall., Pl. Asiat. Rar. (Wallich). 1(2): 24. 1830, *nom. inval.*; Delafosse, Guill. & Je.Kuhn, Bull. Sci. Nat. Geol. 23(Table Gen.): 31. 1830; Wall. ex Endl., Gen. Pl. [Endlicher] 225. 1837.

Type: *Kaempferia elegans* Wall.

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